

Characterization of Atrial Arrhythmic Mechanisms in Body Surface Potential Mapping Computer Models

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Abstract—Atrial tachycardia (AT), atrial flutter (AFL) and atrial fibrillation (AF) are among the most common cardiac arrhythmias and are driven by localized sources (ectopic focus in AT, macro-reentrant circuit in AFL and rotors in AF) that can be targeted for ablation. We aimed to characterize such mechanisms from the non-invasive perspective of body surface potential mapping (BSPM), using realistic computer models. Dominant frequency (DF) maps were studied to estimate the frequency of the driving mechanism (f_{drive}) and to analyze its spatio-temporal distribution. Phase singularity points (SPs) were detected in phase maps and their distribution and rotational patterns were compared between arrhythmias. The f_{drive} s were more expressed on the anterior portion of the torso for the right atrium and on the posterior portion for the left atrium. AF models presented distinct f_{drive} regions, with more regions occupying a significantly smaller portion of the torso. Rotational activity was detected in all arrhythmias, with increasing levels of spatial-temporal stability (AF, AT and AFL, respectively, with significant differences between AFL and AF). These results can be used to identify the driving mechanisms and, in the future, to locate them in the atria.

Keywords—atrial fibrillation, atrial flutter, atrial tachycardia, body surface potential mapping, non-invasive

I. INTRODUCTION

Supraventricular tachyarrhythmias, including focal atrial tachycardia (AT), atrial flutter (AFL) and atrial fibrillation (AF), are among the most common cardiac arrhythmias in the world and can pose serious risks, such as an increased chance of thromboembolic events [1].

These arrhythmias are driven by localized sources, which can be targeted in radio-frequency ablation therapy to restore sinus rhythm [1]: AT is maintained by ectopic foci. AFL is driven by a macro-reentrant circuit, localized typically, but not obligatorily, around the cavotricuspid isthmus. AF has been shown to be maintained by ectopic, re-entrant circuits and functional rotors, which appear preferably when structural and/or functional atrial remodeling occurs [2].

Non-invasive characterization of the distinct driving sources' mechanism, using body surface potential mapping (BSPM), might be an important auxiliary tool for treatment strategy planning [3]. In this study, we aimed to characterize non-invasively three atrial arrhythmia mechanisms - ectopic

activity (AT), macro-reentrant circuit (AFL) and functional reentry (AF) - generated by realistic mathematical models to differentiate them from the perspective of BSPM.

II. METHODS

The methodology is summarized in Fig 1. Computer-generated BSPMs representing the different arrhythmic mechanisms were processed in time, frequency and phase domains, obtaining maps from which specific characteristics were extracted. All analyses were made in Python 3.6.

Fig. 1. General block diagram

A. Computer Modeling

A realistic three-dimensional model of the atrial anatomy composed by 284,578 nodes and 1,353,783 tetrahedrons ($673.4 \pm 130.3 \mu\text{m}$ between nodes) was used to simulate the electrical behavior of the atria in arrhythmic conditions. 19 simulations represented arrhythmias originated by three distinct mechanisms: AT (4 simulations) driven by an ectopic focus; AFL (4 simulations) driven by a macro-reentrant circuit; AF (11 simulations) driven by functional rotors [4]. BSPMs were obtained by solving the forward problem with the boundary element method (sampling frequency = 500 Hz), resulting in 771 data points, of which 567 points were selected to represent a realistic measurement (excluding points inside the waist, neck or arms).

B. Preprocessing

Data points were reshaped into a two-dimensional configuration by projecting their positions on a cylinder. The cylinder was unwrapped and the points were interpolated into a 30 x 65 grid using cubic splines. A 4th order band-pass Butterworth filter was applied between 2 and 20 Hz, covering the spectral components related to the atrial arrhythmic mechanisms [5].

C. Frequency analysis

The frequencies of the driver mechanisms (f_{drive}) were estimated using a combination of analyses in time and frequency with spatial information from the BSPM.

Activation times were detected using a wavelet transform modulus maxima approach [6]. The average activation frequency was estimated as the inverse of the average interval between activation times. The spectral content for each data point was estimated via Welch periodograms (segments of 2.7 s, with Hanning window, zero-padded to 2048 points and with 90% overlap; frequency resolution of 0.37 Hz). The dominant frequency (DF) of the spectrum was defined as the peak closest to the average activation frequency, in order to reduce the detection harmonics of the driver frequency.

The f_{drive} was defined as the highest dominant frequency (HDF) along the torso after applying a spatial mask disregarding 2% of the highest DF values to determine the HDF, thus avoiding harmonics. Estimated f_{drives} were compared with the original modeled frequency of the driving mechanism by calculating the absolute error.

The distributions of the DFs on the torso maps were analyzed by calculating the BSPM DF range (HDF-lowest DF) and identifying regions on the BSPM where the f_{drive} is expressed, defined as connected portions of the torso with DF values in the range $f_{\text{drive}} \pm 0.2$ Hz. Binary maps (True = f_{drive} regions) were used to create percentage maps indicating how many models (divided by atrium) had f_{drive} expressed in each torso location. The average numbers and sizes of the regions were used to compare the arrhythmias and identify patterns in the spectral organization.

D. Phase analysis

A 4th order Butterworth narrowband-pass filter (± 1 Hz) was applied on the BSPM signals around f_{drive} to stabilize the atrial activity seen on the surface, especially for AF [7]. The signals were then downsampled to 128 Hz to decrease computation time. Phase was determined via Hilbert transform, defined as the ratio between imaginary and real portions of the results [4].

Phase maps were generated to detect singularity points (SPs), defined as the points around which all the phases converge [6], using a method based on edge detection: endpoints of edges detected by Canny's method were defined as SP candidates [8].

The detection of the SPs is based on the phase progression along 5 rings with varying radii (≈ 2.2 to 13.2 cm) around the SP candidates. Three criteria must be attended in at least two rings for a SP to be detected: the phase should progress in a range of at least π ; the progression should be at least 60% ordered and there should be no phase leaps larger than π [4].

The spatio-temporal distribution of the SPs was analyzed based on filament maps and heatmaps (HMs). A filament is defined as the connection of the SPs in phase maps along with subsequent time instants, around which at least one full cycle of rotation was sustained. Three-dimensional connected component analysis was applied using a kernel of shape 3x3x64 (6.36 cm x 6.63 cm x 0.5 s) to connect and differentiate the individual filaments, with any two SPs belonging to the same region being assigned to the same

filament. HMs are the histogram of the SPs belonging to filaments along time.

The number of cycles and the frequency of filaments were estimated from the edge maps. Regions in HMs concentrating SPs were segmented with connected component analysis; the number, size and density (i.e. % of SPs inside region / Number of points inside region) of each region were calculated.

E. Statistical Analysis

Anderson-Darling normality test was applied to determine the normality of the data. Homogeneity of variances was evaluated using Bartlett's test. If both the normality and homoscedasticity criteria were followed, analysis of variances followed by Tukey's range test was used. Otherwise, Kruskal-Wallis H-test, followed by Dunn's multiple comparison test, were used. Significance was set at $p < 0.05$; values are given in mean \pm se or mean \pm std where indicated with a †.

III. RESULTS

A. Frequency characterization

f_{drive} was estimated with an absolute error of 0.06 ± 0.03 Hz, 0.18 ± 0.07 Hz and 0.45 ± 0.21 Hz for AT, AFL and AF respectively. The characteristics of the regions expressing f_{drive} are given in TABLE I. TABLE I. AF presents a significantly higher number of regions expressing f_{drive} , but the portion of the torso occupied by these regions was significantly smaller than in the other two arrhythmias ($p < 0.05$), where this frequency is expressed in almost the totality of the torso. DF range is significantly larger in AF than in AFL or TA ($p < 0.05$). The distribution of the regions expressing f_{drive} is displayed in Fig. 2 for drivers in the left and right atria (LA and RA, respectively).

TABLE I. CHARACTERISTICS OF DF EXPRESSION ON TORSO

	Number of f_{drive} regions	f_{drive} region size (% of torso)	DF range (Hz) †
AT	1.50 ± 0.50	77.96 ± 20.96	4.7 ± 0.31
AFL	1.00 ± 0.00	97.62 ± 2.10	2.35 ± 0.63
AF	2.64 ± 0.43	22.27 ± 10.63	2.86 ± 0.15

Fig. 2. Distribution of regions expressing the estimated simulation frequency on the torso, for the models in the LA (top) and RA (bottom)

B. Phase characterization

The numbers of filaments per second, their duration and frequency of rotation are given in TABLE II. No significant differences were encountered when comparing the number of filaments per second; filament duration was significantly shorter in AF than in the other two arrhythmias ($p < 0.05$). The most temporally stable filaments appeared in AFL, followed by AT. The average frequency of rotation around filaments is within 0.5 Hz of f_{drive} in 73.68% and within 1.0 Hz in 89.47% of the models. Fig. 3 shows examples of filaments for all the arrhythmias.

Fig. 3. Representative examples of filaments in AT (a), AFL (b) and AF (c). Each color represents a different filament. IVC: inferior vena cava; CCW: counter-clockwise; RIPV: right inferior pulmonary vein

TABLE II. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FILAMENTS IN EACH ARRHYTHMIA

	Filaments/s	Duration (% of signal)	Frequency (Hz)
AT	1.25 ± 0.29	78.42 ± 13.8	3.96 ± 0.22
AFL	0.96 ± 0.31	90.98 ± 9.02	4.51 ± 0.42
AF	1.16 ± 0.20	38.40 ± 10.42	5.68 ± 0.30

The characteristics of SP regions in HMs are given in TABLE III. While no differences in the number of regions were found ($p = 0.11$), their sizes are significantly smaller in AF than AFL ($p < 0.01$). There was no significant difference in the number of SPs per second; differences appear between AF and AFL in the density of SPs ($p < 0.01$), with AFL presenting higher values, indicative of higher spatio-temporal stability. AT presents intermediate values of region size and SP density between the other two arrhythmias. The distribution of SPs in HMs is displayed in Fig. 4 for the models in the LA and RA

TABLE III. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SP CLUSTERS IN HEATMAPS

	# of SP clusters	Cluster size (% of torso)	SP density
AT	4.25 ± 1.03	0.64 ± 0.14	2.25 ± 0.48
AFL	2.00 ± 0.00	0.44 ± 0.23	10.79 ± 2.71
AF	10.64 ± 2.11	0.85 ± 0.14	0.62 ± 0.11

Fig. 4. Distribution of SPs on the torso, for the models in the LA (top) and RA (bottom)

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this work, analyses performed in the frequency and phase domains were used to characterize the BSPM patterns from three different atrial arrhythmia mechanisms. We developed a unified methodology to estimate the driver mechanism's frequency and extended the phase analysis to encompass all three arrhythmias, allowing the non-invasive characterization and direct comparison of the mechanisms.

The distribution of the DFs on the BSPM was almost uniform for TA and AFL, while AF had more variant patterns with larger DF ranges, highlighting its complexity. The distribution of f_{drive} on the torso followed similar patterns as in other studies [3,9], with most RA models presenting f_{drive} regions on the anterior portion of the torso and most LA models, on the posterior portion.

In this study, stable rotors on BSPM were detected not only in AF and AFL, as reported before [4,10], but also in AT. Filaments were the most stable in AFL, where they were concentrated in few regions with a high number of SPs, which can be explained by the anchoring of macro-reentrant circuits in anatomical structures. AT presented filaments with intermediate duration and stability when compared to the other arrhythmias, although the driving mechanism is an ectopic focus, generating centrifugal wavefronts. While other similar works did not detect this behavior [4], our setting to analyze the phase progression around SPs revealed relevant patterns along circles with radii larger than 2 cm.

Average filament durations in AF were much shorter than in the other two arrhythmias. This is related to the limited field of view of the BSPM, which can hide stable rotors (Fig. 5), to the spatial resolution of the BSPM and to the large number of shorter filaments, unique in AF models.

Fig. 5. Example of an AF stable SP outside the field of view of the BSPM (driver in the RA appendage). In these cases, the average duration of filaments is low, since only short filaments are measured

The current results allow the identification of specific patterns for each driving mechanism, which could be further explored before patient treatment. The methodology described here is currently being applied to patient data [9] and might allow clinicians to obtain valuable information on the driving mechanism before interventions. An example of a DF map from an AF patient is displayed in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. DF map from a sample AF patient

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